

TEACHER'S FREEZING IN HIGHER EDUCATION: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF MALE AND FEMALE TEACHERS

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Abstract

*The purpose of this study is to find out male and female higher education teachers experiencing freezingness. Comparing the teacher-freezing of male and female higher education instructors on each aspect of teacher-freezing and their overall freezing was the aim of the study. For the study, 100 higher education instructors— 50 male 50 female—were chosen at random from a variety of higher education institutions in the Ghaziabad Distt.Uttar Pradesh. The Teacher-freezing Scale (TFS), created by **Dr. Haseen Taj** in 1996, was used to evaluate the teacher-freezing of both male and female college instructors.*

The study's conclusions showed that overall, male and female higher education instructors exhibit almost the same degree of teacher-freezing. Compared to their counterparts, male higher education instructors were shown to be more frozen on the psychological dimension of teacher-freezing. On the otherhand female higher education instructors were shown to be more frozen on the social dimension of teacher-freezing. Furthermore, when it comes to the intellectual, Physical and moral aspects of teacher-freezing, male and female higher education teachers exhibit almost the same degree of this Freezing.

Keywords: *Teacher-freezing , male, female, degree college teachers, Dimensions of teacher-freezing*

INTRODUCTION OF STUDY

Teachers' freezingness describes the unused or underused intellectual, Physical, Psychological, Social and Moral potential of the teachers .It is just like the stagnation of

learning process. There is unwillingness of educators to embrace innovative concepts, procedures, or technological advancements, especially in higher education. Hesitancy or reluctance to accept changes in instructional strategies, curriculum, or institutional regulations are common characteristics of this problem. The word "freezingness" comes from **Kurt Lewin's** theory of change management. In this theory, "freezing" refers to the inertia that happens when people or organizations resist changing their habits and comfort zones.

In higher education, "freezingness" among teachers is a serious problem that affects student involvement, institutional development, and the efficacy of instruction. Stakeholders can identify the root cause which can range from institutional and environmental limitations to psychological and cognitive barriers. Teachers Freezing is difficult situation for teachers to adjust as per the the quickly shifting needs of education, which eventually has an impact on both their professional development and the academic achievements of their students.

After studied a number of research papers and thesis, Researcher identified the Research Gap about there is a dearth of male and female higher education teachers freezingness on dimensionwise. In this paper Researchers wants to compare the level of freezing between male and female higher education teachers, in terms of their Intellectual, Psychological, Physical, Social and Moral dimension of Freezing.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Jena, P.C. (2011) has made a study on the topic "Teacher Freezingness in Relation to Self-Esteem and Social Identity of Secondary School Teachers of Kendriya Vidyalayas".

The result depicts that there is a significant difference between male and female science instructors' social identities and levels of teacher freezingness. However, there was no discernible difference between male and female arts teachers' social identities and teacher freezingness.

Saxena S. L. & Jain R.K. (2013) have conducted a study on the topic "Effect of Medium of Instruction on Teacher Freezingness of Higher Secondary School Teachers". The results demonstrated that the medium of instruction had a significant impact on teachers' degrees of freezingness. English-medium school instructors were found to be more freezed than Hindi-medium school teachers, while male teachers were found to be more freezed than female teachers.

Dhull Indira & Poonam (2015) have conducted a study on the topic "Teacher Freezing Among Secondary School Teachers". The results showed that male teachers were more likely

than female teachers to experience freezing. Additionally, government teachers encountered more freezing than private teachers.

Kumar Dinesh & Kamini (2016) conducted a study on the topic “Teacher freezing of special educators in relation to their job satisfaction”. The findings showed that there was no discernible difference in teacher frozen and special educators' work satisfaction. Additionally, there was no discernible difference between the job satisfaction and teacher freezing of male and female special educators.

Prakash Chandra Jena (2018) carried out research entitled “Teacher Freezingness: does it make any differences in teaching and learning”. According to the researcher's findings, men and female science teachers differ in their levels of teacher freezing. Female science teachers have high teacher freezingness in comparison to male science teachers because participation, organization and resistance in teaching profession among male teachers is more than female teachers.

Basu, Susmita & Banerjee, Debasri (2020) have conducted a study on the topic “Do gender affect freezing”. The researcher discovered that when comparing the degree of freezing proneness between the sexes, there is a significant difference between male and female teachers. Female teachers are less likely to freeze than their male counterparts.

Jain Reena and Chaudhary Neha (2022) carried out research entitled “A Study of Teacher Freezing of Government and Private Secondary School Teachers”. Study show that Male and female secondary school instructors are not significantly different from one another. Therefore, it was found that male and female secondary school teachers do not differ in their degree of teacher freezing.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Statement Of The Problem

Teacher Freezing in Higher Education: A Comparative Study of Male and Female Teachers

Operational Definition of Variable : Teacher freezing

“Teacher freezing is the overall unused, under used and stagnated psychological, intellectual, physical, social and moral potentialities of the teachers.” Taj Haseen

Methodology used: The descriptive survey method of research was employed in this study.

Population, Sample and Sampling Technique: Stratified random sampling technique was used to draw samples from the population. 100 teachers were chosen from the Degree

colleges of Ghaziabad Distt. Out of 50 male teachers and 50 female teachers were taken as a sample.

Tools to be used: Male and female higher education teachers' freezing was evaluated using the "Teacher Freezing Scale," a standardised Tool created by **Dr. Haseen Taj (1996)** of Bengaluru University's Department of Education.

Statistical Methods: The mean, S.D., an t-test are used to examine the hypothesis.

Study-delimitation

1. 100 teachers are included in the study only.
2. Only male and female are included in the study.
3. Single variable of teacher freezing is included in the study.
4. Only higher education Teachers in the Ghaziabad distt. is included in the study.

OBJECTIVES & HYPOTHESIS OF STUDY

Objective-1: To compare teacher-freezing of higher education teachers with respect to male and female .

H01: There is no significant difference in teacher-freezing of higher education teachers with respect to male and female.

Table No.1

Group	No.	Mean	S.D.	t-value	table value	Result at 0.05 level of significance
Male	50	264.77	27.24	0.031	1.96	Non significant
Female	50	265.06	16.74			

Table No.1 show that mean of male teachers is 264.77 and S.D.is 27.24 while mean of female teachers is 265.06 and S.D.is 16.74. Obtained ‘t’ value is 0.031 which is less than the table value and it is non significant at 0.05 level of significance, so the null hypothesis has been accepted and it has been concluded that There is no significant difference in teacher-freezing of higher education teachers with respect to male and female.

Objective-2: To compare teacher-freezing of higher education teachers on intellectual-freezing dimension with respect to male and female.

H02: There is no significant difference in higher education teachers on intellectual-freezing dimension with respect to male and female.

Table No. 2

Group	No.	Mean	S.D.	t-value	table value	Result at 0.05 level of significance
Male	50	90.12	21.36	0.75	1.96	Non significant
Female	50	88.01	9.38			

Table No.2 show that mean of male teachers is 90.12 and S.D.is 21.36 while mean of female teachers is 88.01and S.D.is 9.38. Obtained ‘t’ value is 0.75 which is less than the table value and it is non significant at 0.05 level of significance, so the null hypothesis has been accepted and it has been concluded that There is no significant difference in higher education teachers on intellectual-freezing dimension with respect to male and female.

Objective-3: To compare teacher-freezing of higher education teachers on psychological-freezing dimension with respect to male and female.

H03: There is no significant difference in higher education teachers on psychological-freezing dimension with respect to male and female.

Table No. 3

Group	No.	Mean	S.D.	t-value	table value	Result at 0.05 level of significance
Male	50	65.50	14.28	2.32	1.96	Significant
Female	50	69.81	5.23			

Table No.3 show that mean of male teachers is 65.50 and S.D.is 14.28 while mean of female teachers is 69.81 and S.D.is 5.23.Obtained ‘t’ value is 2.32 which is more than the table value and it is significant at 0.05 levelof significance,so the null hypothesis has been rejected and it has been concluded that There is significant difference in higher education teachers on psychological-freezing dimension with respect to male and female.

Objective-4: To compare teacher-freezing of higher education teachers on social-freezing dimension with respect to male and female.

H04: There is no significant difference in higher education teachers on social-freezing dimension with respect to male and female.

Table No. 4

Group	No.	Mean	S.D.	t-value	table value	Result at 0.05 level of significance
Male	50	22.18	7.05	2.15	1.96	Significant
Female	50	19.08	6.17			

Table No.4 show that mean of male teachers is 22.18 and S.D.is 7.05 while mean of female teachers is 19.08 and S.D.is 6.17. Obtained ‘t’ value is 2.15 which is more than the table value and it is non significant at 0.05 levelof significance, so the null hypothesis has been rejected and it has been concluded that There is a significant difference in higher education teachers on social-freezing dimension with respect to male and female.

Objective-5: To compare teacher-freezing of higher education teachers on physical-freezing dimension with respect to male and female.

H05: There is no significant difference in higher education teachers on physical-freezing dimension with respect to male and female.

Table No. 5

Group	No.	Mean	S.D.	t-value	table value	Result at 0.05 level of significance
Male	50	22.64	6.76	0.16	1.96	Non significant
Female	50	22.48	2.22			

Table No.5 show that mean of male teachers is 22.64 and S.D.is 6.76 while mean of female teachers is 22.48 and S.D.is 2.22. Obtained ‘t’ value is 0.16 which is less than the table value and it is non significant at 0.05 level of significance, so the null hypothesis has been accepted and it has been concluded that There is no significant difference in higher education teachers on physical-freezing dimension with respect to male and female.

Objective-6: To compare teacher-freezing of higher education teachers on moral-freezing dimension with respect to male and female.

H06: There is no significant difference in higher education teachers on moral-freezing dimension with respect to male and female.

Table No. 6

Group	No.	Mean	S.D.	t-value	table value	Result at 0.05 level of significance
Male	50	39.93	9.49	0.21	1.96	Non significant
Female	50	39.66	4.51			

Table No.6 show that mean of male teachers is 39.93 and S.D.is 9.49 while mean of female teachers is 39.66 and S.D.is 4.51. Obtained ‘t’ value is 0.21 which is less than the table value and it is non significant at 0.05 level of significance, so the null hypothesis has been accepted and it has been concluded that There is no significant difference in higher education teachers on moral-freezing dimension with respect to male and female.

CONCLUSIONS AND FINDINGS

Overall, it can be concluded that the degree of teacher-freezing experienced by male and female higher education teachers is Almost the same. The sole difference between them is the Psychological and Social aspect of teacher-freezing. When it comes to the psychological aspect of teacher-freezing, male higher education teachers are more frozen than their female counterparts. . This finding also supports the finding of **Basu, Susmita(2020)**-In the same manner,when it comes to the Social aspect of teacher-freezing, female higher education teachers are more frozen than their male counterparts. This finding also supports the finding of **Rawat, Leena (2021)**.

There may be so many reasons behind the Psychological and Social freezing of male & female higher education teachers. As negative attitude, job dissatisfaction,lack of professional and organizational commitment, lack of motivation, burden of domestic responsibilities ,traditions & rituals etc.may freeze male and female higher education teachers.

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